

CONSUMERS' BEHAVIOUR TOWARDS THERMAL ENERGY SYSTEMS ADOPTION: FINDINGS FROM THE TESSe2b EUROPEAN PROJECT

Spyridon Karytsas^{1*}, Olympia Polyzou¹ and Constantine Karytsas¹

1: Geothermal Energy Department, RES Division, Center for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving, 19th km Marathonos Av., 19009, Pikermi, Greece
e-mail: spkary@cres.gr, www.cres.gr

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1. INTRODUCTION

The residential building sector is responsible for a large proportion of the energy consumption worldwide, mainly due to heating, cooling and Domestic Hot Water (DHW) needs. TESSe2b system is the outcome of a Horizon 2020 funded project intending to deal with the above issue, through the enhancement of energy efficiency in buildings. Its aim is to enable the optimal use of renewable energy sources (RES) and to provide a solution for correcting the mismatch that often occurs between the supply and demand of energy in residential buildings. The target of TESSe2b is to design, develop, validate and demonstrate a modular and low cost thermal storage technology based on solar collectors and highly efficient heat pumps for heating, cooling and DHW production. The idea is to develop advanced compact integrated PCM (Phase Changing Material) TES (Thermal Energy Storage) tanks exploiting RES (solar and geothermal in particular) in an efficient manner, coupled with enhanced PCM BHEs (Borehole Heat Exchangers) that will utilize the increased underground thermal storage and maximize the efficiency of the GSHP (Ground Source Heat Pump).

A key-issue regarding the success of the technology's diffusion is consumers' behaviour. The present study aims to examine the factors that affect thermal energy systems' adoption through consumers' self-reported behaviour, based on the socio-cognitive theory.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A behavioural survey was performed in three EU Member States (Greece, Spain and Portugal) between June 2016 and February 2017. The collection of the developed questionnaire was performed through the project's and partners' websites and social media. It should be mentioned that although the collected sample is not totally representative of the population, since internet surveys do not create samples as representative as telephone or face-to-face surveys [1], it can provide a good basis [2] for the examination of the factors that affect the issues under examination.

In total, 400 fully completed responses were collected: 159 from Greece, 109 from Portugal and 132 from Spain. Separate statistical analysis (SPSS 24) was performed for each country, including simple descriptive statistics for the initial analysis, and procedures such as chi-square tests, non-parametric Mann-Whitney tests and binary and ordinal logistic regressions (in total 24 regression models: eight different investigated issues for each one of the three countries) in order to examine the effect of socioeconomic and residence characteristics on issues such as a) measurement of thermal energy use, b) previous investments in thermal energy systems (conventional or RES) and storage and c) adoption perceptions and intentions for the TESSe2b solution. In addition, chi-square tests and Kruskal-Wallis tests were applied to evaluate the existence of any differences between the three countries' responses.

3. RESULTS

In Greece and Spain, about 35% of the respondents measure and record their use of thermal energy; the equivalent percentage in Portugal is lower than 20%, presenting, in fact, a statistically significant difference with the other two countries. The respondents of the three countries present similar results concerning investments in thermal energy systems in the past five years (40-50%), investments in thermal energy systems using RES in the past five years (22-33%, with the positive responses from Portugal being lower on a statistical significant level) and investments in thermal energy storage in the past year (10-14%). In all countries, the majority of the respondents agree that the TESSe2b system can offer benefits, while there is a positive attitude concerning adoption intention of the system. Respondents state that they would be willing to pay (WTP) up to € 6,000 for the installation (with Portuguese WTP being lower on a statistically significant level, compared to the Spanish respondents), while an acceptable payback period of the installation cost would be up to five years.

The statistical analysis also reveals the different socioeconomic and residence characteristics affecting in a statistically significant level the examined themes. Although the results slightly differ for each issue under investigation among the three countries, a general approach is that respondents a) with: a higher than average income, a high level of education, an occupation relevant to energy/ environment and b) living in a residence that: is self-owned, outside urban areas, newly constructed, not in an apartment building and has an higher than average size are more likely to measure and record their thermal energy use and to have invested in thermal energy systems (either conventional or using RES) and storage.

The factors that have been found to affect the issues concerning the installation of TESSe2b system are in general common with the abovementioned characteristics, with one difference and two additions. Specifically, respondents living in older residences, using conventional sources for heating and DHW (heating oil, natural gas, electricity) and spending a higher than average percentage of their income for household energy needs are more likely to have a more positive benefit perspective and adoption intention and to present a higher level of WTP and acceptable payback period for the TESSe2b system.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The present study examines the socioeconomic and residence characteristics that affect thermal energy use measurement, investments in thermal energy systems and storage and installation of the TESSe2b system (perceived benefits, adoption intention, WTP, acceptable payback period). The findings of the study contribute to the understanding of the behavioural patterns of consumers regarding the selection and installation of residential thermal energy systems.

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